

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF NIGERIAN MANUFACTURING COMPANIES

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of capital structure on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post facto research design using panel data extracted from the 26 selected listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria out of 52 listed manufacturing companies in NEG as at 31st December, 2023. Purposive and stratified sampling techniques were used to select 26 listed manufacturing companies. Panel data were extracted from the annual reports of the selected listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. Descriptive statistics, correlation, Variance Inflation factors and inferential statistics were used to analyze panel data. The study found that: Debt-Equity Ratio, Debt Asset Ratio, Capital Gearing Ratio, Interest Coverage and Firm Size have insignificant influence on Asset Turnover ratio with $t= 0.49$ ($pv=0.621$); -1.08 ($pv=0.278$); -0.06 ($pv=0.952$), 0.24 ($pv=0.807$) and 0.81 ($pv=0.419$). Wald statistic value of 236.24 ($pv=0.000$) showed that all capital structure variables have joint significant effect on Asset Turnover ratio. DER, DAR and FS have significant impact on Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization with t -statistic of 1.96 ($pv=0.050$); 4.48 ($pv= 0.000$) and 9.15 ($pv=0.000$) while CGR and ICR have insignificant impact on EBITDA with t -statistic value of -0.51 ($pv=0.613$) and 1.46 ($pv=0.144$) respectively. The wald test showed statistic value of 103.11 ($pv=0.000$) indicated that all capital structure variables have significant impact on EBITDA. The study concluded that capital structure mix have significant influence on the financial performance of the selected listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study therefore recommended that listed manufacturing firms should optimally utilize the capital structures mix in order to improve their financial performance.

Keywords: Capital Structure, Asset Turnover Ratio, EBITDA

Introduction

The manufacturing sector is a crucial component of the Nigeria economy, contributing significantly to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and providing employment opportunities for millions of Nigerians. However, the sector has faced numerous challenges in recent years, including inadequate funding, inefficient management and intense competition. One of the critical factors that can affect the performance of manufacturing firms is their capital structure. Capital structure refers to the mix of debt and equity financing used by a firm to fund its operations and investments. A firm's capital structure can influence its cost of capital, risk profile and ultimately, its financial performance. Investors and potential investors will be obliged to invest their hard-earned savings in a company that promises to make a return that will change their wealth position at a point in time. The essence of capital structure decisions is to ensure the right combination of financing resources that will yield maximum return without necessarily

hampering the interest of stakeholders (Fatoki, Wajula & Waweru, 2021). Firms need huge investment outlays to meet their investment objectives. The choice of sources of funds is subject to multivariate factors. Financing sources can be internal sources such as retained earnings and external sources such as loans in the form of debt or issued shares in the capital market (Hayati, & Muchtar, 2022). Theoretical and empirical researches have existed in capital structure since the path-breaking study of Miller and Modigliani published in 1958 (Mahmoud, 2017). Existing pieces of literature on capital structure mix are majorly on the developed nations rather than developing nations and this remains gaps in the extant literature (Mahmoud, 2017).

Statement of the Problems

Previous pieces of literatures have explored capital structure impacts on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The choice of capital structure mix is considered to have a significant effect on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria (Ogunade, 2019). There is no consensus as regards the impact of capital structure mix on financial performance. Owolabi et al, (2021) affirmed that equity had a positive insignificant influence on financial performance. Suleiman et al, (2022) affirmed that share capital has a positive insignificant influence on the financial performance of listed money deposit banks in Nigeria. Bassey et al, (2016) used retained earnings as an independent variable.

Onoja and Ovayioza (2015) affirmed that long-term debt has a positive insignificant variant with the firm's financial performance proxy as Return on Asset and Return on Equity. Olaoye and Adesina (2022) used the Debt-Equity ratio, short-term debt, and long-term debt to Total assets as independent variables. Return on Equity and Return on Assets were used as a proxy for financial performance. Olaoye and Adesina (2022) established that DER has insignificant negative effect on Return on Asset while it has negative significant influence on return on equity. Kim *et al.* (2023) posited that Current and debt-equity ratios have negative impact on the financial performance of the companies. Anozie *et al.* (2023) also used short term debt to total asset ratio, total debt to total equity ratio and Long-term debt to total asset ratio. Long-term Debt to total asset ratio adversely influenced the Return on Asset and Short term to total asset and Total debt to total equity had positive significant. The debt financing decreases the profit of the entity (Narasaih, 2020). Long term debt and Total debt decrease the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Short term debt ratio and Long-term debt ratio have negative influence on ROA and ROE. The optimal capital structure mix that will enhance corporate performance remains the controversial issues as many literatures have differences as to appropriate sources of finance (whether external or internal sources). This study aims to fill this knowledge gap by investigating the effect of capital structure on financial performance of selected listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to determine the impact of capital structure on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The following are the specific objectives of the study:

- i. Investigate the effect of capital structure on Asset Turnover Ratio of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the influence of capital structure on Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Statement of Hypotheses

Based on the objectives stated above, the following tentative statement is awaiting empirical testing:

Ho1: Capital structure has no significant effect on Asset Turnover of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria

Ho2: Capital structure has no significant effect on Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Capital Structure

Ajayi *et al.* (2021) describe capital structure as the company's chosen combination of debt, preferred stock, and common equity for the goal of generating cash. The corporation must make the required investments to at least stay in business and demonstrate some growth. The capital structure of a firm is significant because it impacts on ability to meet the needs of its stakeholders. Ajibola *et al.* (2018) refer to capital structure as a structure which reflects each component of finance from equity to debt that a company uses in financing its operations. The problem of choosing between equity and debt is faced by many firms, especially in funding their long-term investment opportunities. Capital structure refers to the financing methods used by a company to fund its operations and growth, which includes both equity and debt (Dada & Ghazali, 2016). Capital structure is an important dimension aspect of corporate finance that plays an essential role in determining a company's financial health and profitability. By employing both equity and debt financing, firms can achieve an optimal balance between risk and return for their stakeholders. Equity financing involves issuing shares of stock to investors in exchange for capital, providing the company with long-term funding but also exposing shareholders to potential losses if the business underperforms.

Capital Gearing Ratio: Capital gearing has been variously measured by different literatures through different definitions. Okpe *et al.* (2018) described capital gearing ratio as the relationship between fixed interest capital and ordinary share capital. Fixed interest capital includes preference shares and long-term loans. Gearing is a measure of financial leverage, demonstrating the degree to which a firm's activities are funded by owner's funds versus creditor's funds (Okpe *et al.* 2018 & Usman *et al.* 2019). Kim *et al.* (2023) viewed gearing ratio as leverage or calculated as the ratio between total liabilities to total assets. Usman *et al.* (2019) opined that a firm is geared if the contribution of the creditors is higher than that of equity holders. The choice of capital structure will enhance the equity holders' earnings. This study adopts capital gearing as measure of capital structure of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It is measured as the ratio of debt capital on total equity capital express in percentage.

Interest Coverage Ratio: Interest coverage ratio is described as a ratio similar to time interest earned ratio but preferable to the time interest earned ratio for marking financing analysis (Onuora & Obia, 2018).

Suranta et al. (2023) opined that interest coverage ratio is one of the ratios that can be used to evaluate a company's health or financial difficulties. The ICR is a measure of companies' ability to meet interest payment and is equal to earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT) for a period often one year divided by interest expenses for the same period (Manik, 2016). ICR with a large value shows a good picture of a firm in managing interest payment on its debt. The greater the ratio, the fewer the obstacles it could face in paying the debt because the interest incurred will be borne by earnings before interest and tax (Lestari, 2021). The lender will measure the credibility of the company from its interest coverage ratio (Lestari, 2021). This study uses interest coverage ratio as a measure of capital structure. It is measured as the ratio of Earnings before Interest and Tax on interest expenses.

Debt as a Funding Decision: Debt is indeed a crucial funding decision that organizations often make to finance their operations, investments, or expansions. It involves borrowing money from external sources with the promise of repayment over time, usually with interest. This financial strategy allows companies to leverage their capital structure, manage cash flow, and potentially achieve higher returns on investment (Hayati et al 2022; Smith, 2019).

Financial Performance

The financial performance concept is based on the idea that an organization is a voluntary association of productive assets, including human, physical, and capital resources, to achieve a shared purpose (Akindele et al. 2020). It is said that the essence of performance is the creation of value. Therefore, value creation, as defined by the resource provider, is the essential overall performance criteria for any organization. Financial performance is often compounded by criteria such as profit margin or increased turnover (Akindele et al. 2020). In several researches, the word "performance" and "success" are used interchangeably. Profitability: is also a measure of the financial performance of a company. According to Owolabi and Obida (2012), profitability is defined as the ability of a firm to make profits from all its operating, investing, and financing activities. A firm must be able to generate revenue over direct and indirect costs before it can make a profit. Also, maximizing shareholders' wealth means a firm can pay dividends consistently as a result of the appreciation of the worth of the firm's market share (Olowe, 2018). It is calculated by dividing the net income of a company by its total assets (Olayemi & Fakayode, 2021). The ROA figure shows the effectiveness of a company in converting the money invested into net income. Return on equity is one of the measures of financial performance. The higher the return on equity, the more efficient the company is in generating income from the equity of the shareholders (Owolabi & Obida, 2012).

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on pecking order and static trade of theories

Pecking Order Theory

The pecking order theory developed by Stewart Myers and Nicolas Majluf (1984) is based on the concept that firms prioritize sources of financing their investment. According to the theorists, there is asymmetric information between managers and investors. Thus, investors would want higher returns to compensate

for the risk they are taking and the less information at their disposal (Olayemi & Fakayode, 2021). The theory proposes that a firm has three sources of finance, that is, internal finances, debt, and the issue of new shares. It is based on the pecking order theory that corporations rank their preferred source of funding with internal sources being the most preferred and therefore in circumstances where internal sources are not adequate, a firm will go for debt financing with issuing new shares being the last option which is least preferred (Ngatia, Omondi & Ouma, 2022). The theory is relevant to capital structure as it guides the manufacturing firms on the priority that can be followed about financing projects for improved financial performance which is explained by the findings of the study that an increase in the use of debt capital reduces financial performance (Ngatia et al. 2022).

Internal financing is the cheapest source of financing in contrast to external sources such as debt or equity. Of the two external sources, firms prefer debt financing because of the lower cost of obtaining as opposed to equity financing (Adeoye *et al.* 2021). The theory has no well-defined target debt/equity ratio and each firm's observed debt ratio simply reflects the firm's cumulative requirement for external finance over an extended period (Ajayi *et al.* 2021). According to the pecking order model, the firms will first use internal funds (retained earnings) before issuing debt and will finally only issue equity under duress or when the investment requirement so far exceeds debt capacity that it would lead to excessive leverage (Ajayi *et al.* 2021)

Static Trade-off Theory

The theory was propounded by (Myers & Majluf, 1984). The theory proposes that capital structure predicts that firms will choose the mix of debt and equity financing to balance the cost and benefit of debts (Adesola, 2009). It should, however, realize that a company cannot continuously minimize its overall cost of capital by employing debts. A point or a range is reached beyond which debt becomes more expensive because of the increased risk (financial distress) of excessive debt to creditors as well as to shareholders (Myer & Mjaluf, 1984 & Adesola, 2009). When the degree of leverage increases, the risk of creditors also increases and the demand for higher interest is not to grant loans to the company at, once its debt has reached a particular level. Further, the excessive amount of debt makes the shareholder's position very risky. This has the effort of increasing the cost of equity. Thus, up to a point, the overall cost of capital decreases with debt. But beyond that point, the cost of capital will start increasing and therefore it will not be advantageous to employ debt further. There is a combination of debts and equity which minimizes the firm average cost of capital and maximizes the market value per share. The trade-off between the cost of capital and Earnings Per Share (EPS) sets the maximum limit to the uses of debt. However, other factors should be evaluated to determine the appropriate capital structure for a company. STT offers a partial explanation of the factors that determine a firm's choice of leverage.

Empirical Review

Olaoye et al. (2020) evaluated the effect of capital structure on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study employed the ex post facto research design. The population

of the study consisted of the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria made up of 71 companies as at 31st December 2017 according to the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), which formed the entire population of the study. The study adopted descriptive and inferential statistics. The finding of the study indicated that capital structure influences the performance of the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study concluded that capital structure has a significant relationship with the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Arikekpar (2020) evaluated the impact of capital structure on firm performance using a fixed effect regression model to test the significant impact of capital structure on a firm's performance for 5 years (2014-2018). The study used ROA, ROE, and EPS as proxies for a firm's performance and equity ratio to debt ratio as indicators for capital structures. The study revealed that capital structure has a positive significant effect on the financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria.

Variables such as: asset turnover, capital gearing, EBITDA and interest coverage were not used in the study. In addition, the study did not use control variables.

Ajayi et al. (2021) focused on capital structure and firm value, using a study of selected listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. A historical research design and an ex post facto research design were used in this study. This research used panel data, which includes cross-sectional and time series data. The population of the study was the entire manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Ten listed manufacturing businesses in Nigeria were chosen using a basic random selection approach to evaluate the link that exists between Capital Structure and Firm Value. The study used descriptive analysis, ordinary least square regression method, and correlation. The results revealed that the Debt Ratio and Firm Size (Independent variables) have a favourable impact on Firm Value (Dependent variable), but the Proprietary Ratio and Retention Ratio have no such impact. This positive relationship suggests that financial leverage, as measured by the Debt ratio, is a significant predictor of the firm's Total Value. This indicates that businesses make proactive efforts to increase sales and value by successfully employing debt finance.

Olayemi and Fakayode (2021) examined the effect of capital structure on the financial performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study covered ten companies for a period of seven years that is 2013 to 2019. Panel data analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The independent variables used are total debt to total asset ratio (TDTAR), long-term debt to total assets (LDTAR), short-term debt to total assets (SDTAR), and total debt to total equity (TDTER) while the dependent variables are return on asset (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). The results of the study showed that SDTAR and LDTAR have positive but insignificant effects on ROA, and TDTAR has a negative significant effect on ROA and ROE, respectively. Also, TDTAR and TDTER have negative insignificant effects on ROE. The study concluded that SDTAR, LDTAR, and TDTER have no significant effect on ROA and ROE, but TDTAR influences ROA.

Adeoye et al. (2021) studied the optimality of the financing structure adopted by firms as germane in attaining a firm's profit and wealth maximization goals. An ex-post facto study was conducted on selected ten (10) consumers and industrial goods-producing firms in Nigeria using a regression estimate between

1997 and 2017, resulting in 210 firm-year observations of balanced panel data. The study found that capital structure significantly influenced Tobin's Q; debt-equity ratio and short-term debt-total asset ratio significantly and positively affected Tobin's Q. It was concluded that capital structure influenced the profitability and value of firms.

Olaoye and Adesina (2022) aimed to establish the effect of capital mix on the financial performance of 10 chosen manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG) for 12 years period, spanning 2009 to 2020. Secondary data were extracted from the audited accounts and reports of the chosen firms. This research employed descriptive and inferential statistical analyses for data estimation. The results of this work revealed that debt about equity (DER) has an insignificant adverse effect on the return on asset (ROA) of the selected firms. Contrarily, DER has a direct significant effect on return on equity (ROE) and a direct insignificant effect on the net profit margin (NPM) of the sampled manufacturing companies. Total debt to total assets (TDTA) has a positive but insignificant effect on all the financial performance indicators. The study also found that short-term debt to total assets (SDTA) and long-term debt to total assets (LDTA) have negative effects on all the dependent variables. Anozie et al. (2023) examined the impact of capital structure on the financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto research methodology, the short-term debt to total asset, long-term debt to total asset, total debt to total equity, and return on asset variables were investigated as proxies for capital structure and financial performance respectively. These data covered the years 2011 through 2020 and were compiled from the annual financial reports of five Nigerian oil and gas companies. Descriptive statistics and panel regression analysis were used to analyze the data. The analysis findings show that while long-term debt to total assets has a negative significant influence on return on assets, short-term debt to total assets and total debt to total equity have positive insignificant impact on financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Many pieces of literature reviewed have empirically examined the impact of capital structures on financial performance (Ajayi *et al*, (2021); Olayemi & Fakayode (2021) and Olaoye & Adesina, 2022); Adeoye et al, (2021). The finding established a positive significant effect of capital structure on the financial performance of the listed firms in Nigeria. However, previous studies had not distinctly investigated the significant relationship between capital structures and financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria using variables such: Asset turnover and EBITDA as measures of financial performance

Methodology

The study adopted an ex post facto research design. The population for the study comprised all the 52 (fiftytwo) manufacturing companies that are listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NEG)) as of 31st December 2023 (NSE, 2023). The sample size of 26 companies was sampled from the listed manufacturing companies on the Nigeria Exchange Group. Purposive and stratified sampling techniques were adopted to draw the samples from consumer goods, health care, industrial goods, conglomerates, and agriculture between 2014 and 2023. The study used secondary sources of data. The financial statements of the selected companies between financial years from 2014 to 2023 were used to extract panel data for the analysis. The

techniques adopted for the data presentation and analysis include tables with summary and descriptive statistics. Preliminary data tests such as the heteroskedastic test and Hausman test were carried out to determine the appropriate estimation between fixed and random effects. The result of Breusch Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier Test were carried out for confirmation of the Hausman result, judging the appropriateness of either random effect and Pooled OLS with the significant result when $P < 0.05$

Model Specification and Interpretation

This study adopted the model applied by Ajibola et al. (2018) with minor modifications to accommodate more variables to suit the objective of the study. Financial Performance is $f(\text{Capital Structure})$ This was operationalized as follows:

$$\text{ATO} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{DER} + \beta_2\text{DAR} + \beta_3\text{CGR} + \beta_4\text{ICR} + \beta_5\text{FS} + \varepsilon.. \text{iii EBITDA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{DER} + \beta_2\text{DAR} + \beta_3\text{CGR} + \beta_4\text{ICR} + \beta_7\text{FS} + \varepsilon... \text{v Where:}$$

Financial performance = (ATO, EBITDA)

Capital Structure = (DER, DAR, CGR, ICR, FS)

Interpretation of models

Dependent Variables: ATO- Asset Turnover and EBITDA -Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization proxy as the financial performance of the selected firms B_0 = Intercept or constant variable ; $B_1, B_2, B_3, \dots, B_5$ = coefficient of the independent variables considered in the study U_{it} = disturbance or un-estimated error term Where:

DER- Debt-Equity Ratio

DAR- Debt- Assets Ratio

CGR - Capital Gearing Ratio

ICR- Interest Coverage Ratio

FS- Firm Size

Test of Hypotheses Hypothesis One

Capital structures have no significant effect on Asset Turnover of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis One

		Model One		
Random Effect Model				
Variable	Coeff.	SE	t-test	Prob.
Constant	-0.5766	0.94795	-0.61	0.543
DER	0.0092	0.01865	0.49	0.621
DAR	-0.1736	0.16014	-1.08	0.278
CGR	-0.0054	0.00009	-0.06	0.952
ICR	0.0002	0.00085	0.24	0.807
FS	0.1013	0.12541	0.81	0.419
Adj. R ² ; Prob.(F-Stat)	0.5403 (0.0000)			
Diagnostics Test				
Wald-Stat	236.24		0.0000	
Hausman Test	4.09		0.5369	
Breusch-Pagan LM test	1.0000		0.0000	
Heteroskedasticity Test	54.83		0.0000	

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025

The table shows the results of regression analysis of investigating the effect of capital structure on Asset Turnover Ratio of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The results show that debt equity ratio and interest cover ratio have positive relationship with asset turnover ratio of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This means that as debt equity ratio and interest cover ratio increase, there will be increase in asset turnover ratio of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. In addition, there is evidence that all the variables have no significant relationship with asset turnover ratio of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria (DER= 0.0092, t-test= 0.49, $p < 0.05$, DAR= 0.1736, t-test= -1.08, $p < 0.05$, CGR= -0.0054, t-test= -0.06, $p < 0.05$ ICR= 0.0021, ttest= 0.24, $p < 0.05$,FS= -0.103, t-test= 0.81, $p < 0.05$).

The Wald-Test of 280.96 is statistically significant with $p < 0.05$. At the level of significance 0.05, The Wald-Test recorded 280.96 while the probability of the Wald-Test is 0.0000 which is less than 0.05 adopted level of significance indicated that generally, the statistical significance of the model showed that the null hypothesis that Capital structures have no significant effect on Asset Turnover of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis that Capital structure has significant effect on Asset Turnover of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was accepted.

Hypothesis Two

Capital structure has no significant effect on Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

		Model Two		
Random Effect Model				
Variable	Coeff.	SE	t-test	Prob.
Constant	0.0081	985.36	-8.26	0.000
DER	38.06	161.85	1.96	0.050
DAR	725.76	161.85	4.48	0.000
CGR	-462.49	914.05	-0.51	0.613
ICR	125.04	856.94	1.46	0.144
FS	0.0012	1310.65	9.15	0.000
Adj. R ² ; Prob.(F-Stat)	0.353 (0.000)			
Diagnostics Test				
Wald-Stat	103.11		0.0000	
Hausman Test	1.55		0.9067	
Breusch-Pagan LM test	1.000		0.0000	
Heteroskedasticity Test	122.76		0.0000	

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025

The result of Model 5 shows that debt asset ratio, debt asset ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size, have positive relationship with earnings before interest, tax, depreciation and amortization, while capital gearing ratio on the other hand has negative relationship with earnings before interest, tax, depreciation and amortization of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The result also indicates that none of the variables has significant relationship with earnings before interest, tax, depreciation and amortization of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria (DER= 38.06, t-test= 1.96, p< 0.05,DAR= 725.76, t-test= 4.48, p< 0.05,CGR= -462.49, t-test= -0.51, p< 0.05, ICR= 125.04, t-test= 1.46, p< 0.05,FS = 0.0012, t-test= 9.15p< 0.05).

The Wald-Test recorded 103.11while the probability of the Wald-Test is 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 adopted level of significance indicating that on the overall, the statistical significance of the model showed that the null hypothesis of Capital structure has no significant effect on Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was rejected, while the alternate hypothesis that Capital structure has significant effect on Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was adopted.

Discussion of Findings

The study established that capital structure mix have significant influence on asset turn over. Although many literatures reviewed did not consider asset turnover as a measure of financial performance. Base on the *a priori expectation* of the study, it was projected that combination of many capital structure components will improve the quality of asset turnover of the firm. Combination of long and short debt instrument if successfully combined will enhance asset quality of the firm. Empirical study also was carried

out on the effect of capital structure on Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization as proxy for financial performance. The study established that capital structure components have significant effect on EBITDA. This indicated that as the firms optimally utilize the capital structure mix, the better the EBITDA of the firm. Many literatures reviewed did not consider EBITDA as a measure of financial performance and this is one of the gaps created and filled in this study. However, the outcome of this study is in line with a priori expectation. It is therefore affirmed that combination of various capital structure mix enhances the quality of Earnings before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Capital structure components such as debt-equity ratio, debt- asset ratio, capital gearing and interest coverage were regressed again the various financial performance measures such as: Asset Turnover and EBITDA. It was concluded that capital structure components positively influence: Asset Turnover and EBITDA of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The effective combination of various capital structure mix improved the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies. It is therefore recommended that:

- i. Listed manufacturing companies should adopt optimal combination of capital structures in order to improve the quality of asset turnover.
- ii. EBITDA are assumed to reflect economic reality of profitability. Listed manufacturing firms should consider effective combination of capital structures to improve the quality of Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization.

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